

NITRATION OF 5-HYDROXY-4-METHYLCOUMARIN AND 5-HYDROXY-4-METHYLCOUMARIN-6-CARBOXYLIC ACID AND ITS METHYL ESTER.

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5-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin on nitration at 0° affords 5-hydroxy-4-methyl-8-nitrocoumarin and at higher temperatures the 6:8-dinitro derivative. The nitration of 5-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylic acid and its methyl ester affords 8-nitro derivatives, and the 8-nitro-acid on decarboxylation gives 5-hydroxy-4-methyl-8-nitrocoumarin, identical with the mono-nitro product of 4-methyl-5-hydroxycoumarin.

The nitration of coumarin itself and its hydroxy and methoxy derivatives has been investigated by a number of workers (Bleibtren, *Annalen*, 1855, 98, 252; Tage, *Ber.*, 1887, 20, 2110; Morgan, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, 88, 1233; Francis, *Ber.*, 1906, 39, 3803; Clayton, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 97, 1397; Pechmann and Cohen, *Ber.*, 1884, 17, 2136; Pechmann and Obermiller, *ibid.*, 1901, 34, 666; Fries and Lindemann, *Annalen*, 1848, 67, 404; Dey and Krishnamurthi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 5, 197; Dey and Kutti, *Proc. Nat. Inst. Sci.*, 1940, 6, 641). As 5-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin and its derivatives have become recently available (Sethna, Shah and Shah, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 228), it has been thought interesting to study the substitution in such derivatives and to find out the reactivity of 5-hydroxycoumarin nucleus. In this communication, the nitration of 5-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin and 5 hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylic acid and its methyl ester has been investigated.

5-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (Sethna, Shah and Shah, *loc. cit.*) has been nitrated under different conditions. The mono-nitro product, (174-76°) is obtained without difficulty on treating the coumarin with a mixture of concentrated sulphuric acid and nitric acid (*d* 1.42) at 0°-5°.

The product (m.p. 174-75°) is boiled with concentrated ammonia; on acidification the unchanged product is recovered, showing that the nitro group does not enter the pyrone ring (*vide* Clayton, *loc. cit.*). Of the

following alternative structures, (I) is eliminated as OH is always *o-p*-directing. Of the remaining (II) and (III), 5-hydroxy-8-nitro-4-methylcoumarin structure (III) probably represents the product (m.p. 174.76°) as it gives only a feeble ferric chloride colouration since it corresponds to *p*-nitrophenol.

In order to establish the above structure definitely, the nitration of 5-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylic acid and its methyl ester has been studied. In this case, the position 6 is blocked up and the possibility for the entry of nitro group is only 8 or 3 position or both. Methyl 5-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylate (Sethna *et al.*, *loc. cit.*), gives on nitration a mono-nitro product (m.p. 201.2°), which on hydrolysis gives the acid (m.p. 220.21°), identical in all respects to the nitro-acid obtained by the direct nitration of 5-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylic acid (Sethna *et al.*, *loc. cit.*) under the same conditions as in the case of the ester. The nitro-acid (m.p. 220.21°), is boiled with concentrated ammonia; but the original product is recovered on acidification, showing that NO₂ has not entered the pyrone ring. Thus the nitration has been effected in 8-position of the coumarin nucleus in both the acid and the ester, yielding 5-hydroxy-4-methyl-8-nitrocoumarin-6-carboxylic acid (IV) and its ester (V) respectively.

The decarboxylation of the acid (IV) gives a product (m.p. 174.76°) identical in all respects with the nitration product of 5-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin, which is thus definitely proved to be 5-hydroxy-8-nitro-4-methylcoumarin.

The nitration of 5-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin at room temperature gives the dinitro product (m.p. 181.82°). Its behaviour with boiling ammonia shows that none of two NO₂ groups enters the pyrone ring. It has, therefore, been assigned the structure 5-hydroxy-4-methyl-6:8-dinitrocoumarin.

Pechmann and Obermiller (*loc. cit.*) found that in nitration of the 7-hydroxycoumarin, the nitro group had entered the position 8. The same coumarin shows reactivity in 8-position in other reactions also (*vide* Rangaswami and Seshadri, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1937, 6A, 122; Späth and Pailer, *Ber.*, 1935, 68, 941; Baker and Lothian, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 628; 1936, 275). The results of nitration of 5-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin show the

reactivity in 8-position which is *para* to OH in 5-position of the coumarin nucleus. If the fixation of double bonds had taken place under the experimental conditions, the product should have been 6-nitro derivative. In this connection, it may be mentioned that 5-acyloxy-4-methylcoumarins undergo the Fries migration to give 6-acyl derivatives (Sethna, Shah and Shah, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 228, 1424; 1939, 1250). The results of the

present investigation show that 5-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin reacts sometimes in form (A) and sometimes in form (B). Further work to elucidate this point more fully is being undertaken.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

5-Hydroxy-8-nitro-4-methylcoumarin (III).—5-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (0.5 g.), prepared according to the method of Sethna, Shah and Shah (*loc. cit.*), was added to a mixture of nitric acid (*d* 1.42, 0.8 c.c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (1 c.c.), the temperature being kept within 0°-5° by keeping it in ice-bath. The reaction mixture was kept at the same temperature for 1 hour with stirring and the pasty mass then added to water. The product that separated was washed with water and sodium bicarbonate (5%, 5 c.c.), dried and crystallised from acetic acid (charcoal) in golden yellow prisms, m.p. 174-76° (efferv.), yield 0.2 g. It gives slight reddish colour with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found: N, 6.7. C₁₀H₇O₃N requires N, 6.33 per cent.)

The nitro compound was boiled with concentrated ammonia but it was recovered unchanged.

Methyl 5-Hydroxy-8-nitro-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylate (V).—Methyl 5-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylate (4 g.), prepared according to Sethna *et al.* (*loc. cit.*), was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (80 c.c.) and nitric acid (*d* 1.42, 32 c.c.) added drop by drop. It was then refluxed on a water-bath for 20-30 minutes, cooled and crystallised from acetic acid as golden yellow needles, m.p. 201-02°, yield 2 g. A further quantity was recovered from mother-liquor by extracting with ether. (Found: N, 5.13. C₁₂H₉O₇N requires N, 5.0 per cent.)

5-Hydroxy-8-nitro-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylic Acid (IV).—(i). The above ester (0.5 g.) was shaken up with sodium hydroxide (10%, 20 c.c.)

and kept for 60 hours. The solution was filtered and acidified. The solid crystallised from hot water as yellow needles, m.p. 220-21° (efferv.), yield 0.2 g. (Found: N, 5.6. $C_{11}H_7O_2N$ requires N, 5.3 per cent).

(ii) The ester was conveniently hydrolysed by heating the above quantities of the ester and alkali on a water-bath for 20-30 minutes. This method is more convenient for hydrolysis of the ester than (i).

(iii) 5-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylic acid (5 g.) was dissolved in hot glacial acetic acid solution and nitric acid ($d_{15} 1.42$, 40 c.c.) added to it while hot, and then the mixture refluxed on a water-bath for 20-30 minutes. It was cooled, diluted with ice-water, the product was collected, washed and crystallised from water as yellow needles, m.p. 220-21° (efferv.), identical in all respects with 5-hydroxy-8-nitro-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylic acid obtained above, yield 2.4 g. The mixed m.p. was unaffected.

The acid gives effervescence with sodium and potassium bicarbonates forming sparingly soluble salts; it dissolves in alkali with non-fluorescent yellow colour, and gives red colour with alcoholic ferric chloride.

Decarboxylation of 5-Hydroxy-8-nitro-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylic Acid.—The acid (0.8 g.) was heated with water (20 c.c.), glacial acetic acid (8 c.c.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (4 c.c.) in a sealed tube for 7-8 hours at 135°-140°. The solution was filtered and extracted with ether. The acetic acid was removed over sodium hydroxide in a vacuum desiccator; the residue crystallised from glacial acetic acid (charcoal) as yellow prisms, m.p. 174-76° (decomp.), yield 0.2 g. The product was identical in all respects with the nitration product of 5-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin described before (mixed m.p.).

5-Hydroxy-6:8-dinitro-4-methylcoumarin.—5-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (1 g.) in acetic acid solution (15 c.c.) was treated with concentrated nitric acid (8 c.c.) dropwise with shaking and cooling under tap. The mixture was left overnight, diluted with water; the product collected and crystallised from aqueous methyl alcohol as yellow prisms, m.p. 181-82°, yield 0.4 g. (Found: N, 10.8. $C_{11}H_6O_7N_2$ requires N, 10.5 per cent).

The dinitrocoumarin (0.2 g.) was dissolved in concentrated ammonia (10 c.c.) and boiled for nearly 3 hours. On acidification, the unchanged product, m.p. 180-82°, was recovered.

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